

Research Capability of San Isidro College Faculty: Intervention Strategies to Write a Research Paper

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ABSTRACT

Research capability is essential in Higher Education Institutions (HEIs) because it advances knowledge, improves the quality of education, and enhances faculty professional development. Assessing research capability is essential for institutional development, relevance, competitiveness, and fostering collaborations and partnerships. This study assessed the research capability of the faculty at San Isidro College. It developed and evaluated intervention strategies aimed at improving their skills in writing and submission of research papers. The study revealed a moderate level of research activity within the institution, with a significant number of faculty members publishing their research in institutional and international journals. However, only a tiny proportion of researchers have a high publication output. Additionally, less than half of the faculty members have moderate research productivity, and more than half of the population has some level of research engagement. Furthermore, the college faculty survey revealed several key findings regarding the need for support and resources to improve research capabilities. Many faculty suggested research advisership, indicating a perceived need for guidance and mentorship. Additionally, faculty members recognized the importance of continuous learning and requested seminars and workshops to enhance their research skills. Moreover, faculty members desired more time and resources allocated towards research activities and recognition and rewards for their research efforts.

Subject Area

Research Writing; Research Capability

Keywords: *Research Capability; Intervention Strategies;
Research Writing*

INTRODUCTION

Research capability refers to the ability of individuals or institutions to conduct research effectively, efficiently, and with a high level of expertise. This capability includes formulating research questions, designing studies, collecting and analyzing data, and disseminating research findings (Salom, 2013). Research capability is crucial in higher education institutions for several reasons. Primarily, research capability allows institutions to contribute to the expanding body of knowledge in various fields. Research leads to the generation of new theories, testing existing ones, acquiring insights, and fostering intellectual growth (Geiger, 2017).

Moreover, research informs teaching practices, allowing educators to incorporate the latest findings and methodologies into their courses. This leads to a higher quality of education, as students benefit from evidence-based teaching and the opportunity to engage in research themselves (Perez et al., 2022). Furthermore, engaging in research enhances the professional development of faculty members. It allows them to deepen their knowledge, stay updated with the latest developments in their field, and contribute to their respective disciplines. Research capability also provides opportunities for collaboration with other researchers, networking, and participating in conferences and academic events (Caingcoy, 2020).

The college faculty of San Isidro College (SIC) should assess their research capability for several reasons. Improving research capability can help the college establish itself as a center of academic excellence. This can attract more students and faculty, increase funding opportunities, and enhance institutional development (Sawyer, 2004). Additionally, in highly competitive academic environments, having research capability is crucial to remain relevant and competitive. It allows faculty members to contribute to the current knowledge base, participate in academic discourse, and maintain credibility and reputation (Ivanenko et al., 2015).

Moreover, faculty members with strong research capabilities can provide students valuable research experiences and mentorship. The research capability cultivates critical thinking skills, problem-solving abilities, and a deeper understanding of their chosen discipline (Christenson et al., 2014; Perez et al., 2022). Furthermore, enhancing research capability can lead to collaborations and partnerships with other institutions nationally and internationally. These collaborations can create opportunities for shared resources, joint research projects, exchange programs, and student mobility (Heimeriks & Schreiner, 2002; Kleyn et al., 2007).

The evidence gap in conducting the study addresses the need for more available comprehensive research and data on the current research capabilities of the faculty members of the college department and practical strategies to improve their research writing skills. The study aims to assess the current research skills and abilities of the faculty members at San Isidro College. The study's goal is to identify the gaps and challenges faced by the faculty in writing research papers and propose intervention strategies to improve their research capabilities.

The study aims to offer evidence-based recommendations and interventions that can enhance the research capabilities of faculty members. By conducting this study, the researchers intend to contribute to the overall enhancement of SIC's research culture and productivity, thereby improving the quality of research outputs from the faculty and promoting academic excellence. Additionally, the study aims to bridge the empirical gap by generating new knowledge and

evidence on the research capability of the faculty, as well as identifying effective intervention strategies to enhance their research paper writing skills and number of submissions.

CONCEPTUAL FRAMEWORK

The study relies on the research methodology concept established by Babbie (2020), which encompasses a systematic approach to designing, conducting, and presenting research, highlighting its essential role in the study. By exploring intervention strategies to improve research capability, the study can examine different research methodologies that can be taught to faculty members to enhance their research skills and increase their research submissions. This concept guided the study's focus on providing practical strategies and techniques for writing research papers.

By anchoring the study on research methodology, the researchers can focus on enhancing the faculty's research capabilities and intervention strategies for writing a research paper. Additionally, anchoring the study on research methodology allows the researchers to explore different intervention strategies that effectively improve the faculty's research capabilities. This will help the faculty members develop the necessary skills to conduct research and write papers effectively (Rubin & Babbie, 2016).

The schematic diagram of the study, as illustrated in Figure 1, illustrates the IPO model of input-process-output. The input variable is the research capabilities of the San Isidro College (SIC) faculty. The formulation of objectives is done within the context of the process variable. Then, the output variable shows the result of the self-evaluation of the college faculty on their research capability and suggested interventions for improving their research output.

Figure 1.
Schematic diagram of the study

STATEMENT OF THE PROBLEM

This study assessed the research capability of the San Isidro College faculty during the Academic Year 2022–2023 with suggestions for intervention to write a research paper.

Specifically, it answered the following sub-problems:

1. What is the publication history of the college faculty at San Isidro College?
2. What is the of research capability does the college faculty have at San Isidro College?
3. What intervention strategies are suggested to compel the college faculty to write a research paper for journal publication?

METHODOLOGY

The study utilized a descriptive research design (Creswell, 2013) to determine the research capability of the San Isidro College (SIC) college faculty and their suggested programs to develop their research skills and improve the number of research submissions. The study's respondents were the 23-college faculty of SIC who voluntarily participated in the study. The study used total population sampling (Lavrakas, 2008) since only a limited number of respondents were available. Total population sampling is an appropriate method for gathering the needed information from the respondents. Table 1 presents the demographic profile of the participants in terms of which school they belong to, designation to an office, years of service, and the number of teaching loads they handle.

Table 1.
Demographic profile of the instructors (N=23)

Demographic Profile		<i>f</i>	%
School	SAS	5	21.74
	SBA	3	13.04
	SED	6	26.09
	SIT	3	13.04
	SOA	2	8.70
	SOE	1	4.35
	SON/SOM	3	13.04
Office Designated	Yes	14	60.87
	No	9	39.13
Years of Service	1 – 3	4	17.39
	3 – 10	10	43.48
	Greater than 10	9	39.13
Number of Teaching Load	Below 18 Units	6	26.09
	18 – 20 Units	2	8.70
	21 – 23 Units	3	13.04
	24 – 26 Units	4	17.39
	27 – 30 Units	8	34.78

The researchers developed and administered a researcher-made questionnaire that explores the research capabilities of the college faculty of SIC. The questionnaire has three parts:

- the demographic profile of the respondents
- the self-assessment of the research capability of the college faculty
- an open space for the suggestions of the college faculty to improve their research capability

The second part of the questionnaire uses a 5-point Likert scale that evaluates the research capability on the different sections of a research paper and has a Cronbach-alpha of 0.604. The scale used the following:

<u>Scale</u>	<u>Range</u>	<u>Qualitative Interpretation</u>
5	4.21–5.00	<i>Most Capable</i>
4	3.41–4.20	<i>More Capable</i>
3	2.61–3.40	<i>Capable</i>
2	1.81–2.60	<i>Less Capable</i>
1	1.00–1.80	<i>Least Capable</i>

Employing a survey questionnaire and adopting a descriptive method (Best & Kahn, 1998), the study utilized an appropriate research process to gather information on the research capability skills of college faculty. Since the study has a small sample size, determining the distribution of the research capability is essential for choosing an appropriate statistical method. Table 2 presents the normality test using Shapiro-Wilk.

Table 2.
Test for normality (Shapiro-Wilk)

Variable	W	p
Research Capability	0.922	0.072

As presented in Table 2, the Shapiro-Wilk test was performed and did not show evidence of non-normality ($W=0.922$, $p=0.072$). Based on the result, the researchers decided to use a parametric test. All data was treated using descriptive statistics and ANOVA to compare sections of the research capability of the college faculty in the different sections of a research paper. The suggestions provided by the college faculty were analyzed using thematic analysis (Kiger & Varpio, 2020). The researchers assigned pseudonyms to the faculty members who responded to the suggestion to protect their identity while maintaining the humanness of their accounts and experiences.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

The study examined the research capability of the San Isidro College faculty. Moreover, the study aims to provide an intervention program to improve research skills and increase the number of research paper submissions by the college faculty. The research implemented the provision of the Data Privacy Act of 2012 in data gathering and storing. The data gathered from respondents was through the survey method. The study used descriptive statistics and ANOVA to treat the quantitative data and thematic analysis for the suggestions of the college faculty.

Publication History of the College Faculty of San Isidro College

Table 3 presents the publication history of the college instructors along with frequency and percentages.

Table 3.
Publication History of the respondents (N=23)

Publication History		f	%
Article Publication	Yes	8	34.78
	No	15	65.22
Journal Publication	Unpublished	5	21.74
	Institutional Journal	8	34.78
	Local/National Journal	0	0.00
	International Journal	3	13.04
	Not Applicable	15	65.22
Institutional Publication	1 – 5	7	30.43
	More than 5	1	4.35
	Not Applicable	15	65.22
International Publication	1 – 5	3	13.04
	More than 5	0	0.00
	Not Applicable	20	86.96
Sole Authorship	1 – 5	6	26.09
	More than 5	2	8.70
	Not Applicable	17	73.91
Collaborative	1 – 5	4	17.39
	More than 5	1	4.35
	Not Applicable	18	78.26

Most college faculty surveyed (65.22%) have yet to gain experience publishing research articles. The percentage indicates that a substantial portion of the population has not been involved in publication (Wa-Mbaleka, 2015). Conversely, a substantial minority (34.78%) have experience in publishing research articles. The percentage suggests that many colleges faculty have successfully published their research work (Tecson-Mendoza, 2015).

The percentage of the college faculty with unpublished research papers is 21.74%. The percentage implies that a significant portion of the surveyed population has conducted research but has yet to publish their findings. The percentage of the college faculty who have published their research in institutional journals is 34.78%. The percentage indicates that a relatively higher number of researchers have successfully published their work within their respective institutions. The data shows that 0% of the college faculty have published their research in local or national journals. The result suggests a need for more participation or interest in disseminating research findings at the local or national level. A percentage of 13.04% of the surveyed population has published their research in international journals. The percentage suggests moderate engagement with the international academic community, as these researchers have successfully contributed to the global knowledge pool by publishing their work in prestigious international journals (Wa-Mbaleka, 2015; Tecson-Mendoza, 2015).

30.43% of the college faculty have 1 to 5 research articles published in an institutional journal. The percentage indicates that a significant portion of the faculty are actively involved in publishing their research in their own institution's journal. It suggests moderate research activity within the institution (Tecson-Mendoza, 2015). The 4.35% of the college faculty have more than five (5) research articles published in an institutional journal. The result implies that only a tiny

percentage of the faculty have a high publication output within their institution. These faculty members may be considered prolific researchers within the institution (Quitoras & Abuso, 2021).

13.04% of the college faculty have 1 to 5 research articles published in an international journal. The percentage suggests that a considerable number of the faculty have successfully published their research in international journals. It indicates a moderate level of engagement with the international research community and a desire to disseminate research on a global scale (Tecson-Mendoza, 2015; Quitoras & Abuso, 2021). None of the faculty has more than five (5) research articles published in an international journal. The result indicates that none of the surveyed individuals have extensive publications in international journals. While there is some engagement with international journals, no prolific researchers are in this particular category (Wa-Mbaleka, 2015).

26.09% of the college faculty have 1 to 5 research articles as sole authorship, while 17.39% have 1 to 5 research articles as collaborative authorship. The percentage indicates that a higher percentage of the faculty prefer sole authorship. 8.70% of the college faculty have more than five (5) research articles as sole authorship, whereas only 4.35% have more than five (5) research articles as collaborative authorship. The percentage suggests that a smaller percentage of the faculty tends to have many articles in both categories. Combining the percentages of 1 to 5 research articles from sole and collaborative authorship showed that 43.48% of the faculty have up to 5 research articles. The percentage implies that less than half of the individuals show moderate research productivity. The combined percentage of more than five (5) research articles from sole and collaborative authorship is 13.04%. The percentage indicates that a relatively small percentage of the faculty are highly productive researchers (Lao et al., 2020; Regla & Ballera, 2021).

Furthermore, the percentage of college faculty with 1 to 5 research articles is higher in sole authorship than in collaborative authorship (26.09% vs. 17.39%). Consequently, it can be inferred that the faculty is likelier to publish papers individually for fewer articles (Lao et al., 2020). On the other hand, the percentage of college faculty with more than five (5) research articles is higher in sole authorship than in collaborative authorship (8.70% vs. 4.35%). The result suggests that the faculty tend to collaborate more for a smaller number of articles (Regla & Ballera, 2021). Combining sole and collaborative authorship, 56.52% of the faculty have published research articles. The percentage implies that more than half of the population under consideration has some level of research engagement (Quitoras & Abuso, 2021). However, if we consider solely the percentage of the college faculty with more than five (5) research articles (sole and collaborative authorship), the number drops to only 13.04%. Comparatively, this indicates that very few faculty achieve a high level of research productivity (Wa-Mbaleka, 2015).

Research Capability of the College Faculty of San Isidro College

Table 4 summarizes the faculty evaluation on their capability on writing an introduction.

Table 4.

Faculty evaluation on the research capability on writing an introduction.

Writing An Introduction	Percentage				
	5	4	3	2	1
Title of the Research Paper	-	30.40	43.50	17.40	8.70
Background of the Study	-	30.40	43.50	17.40	8.70
Framework of the Study	-	13.00	56.50	21.70	8.70
Statement of the Problem	4.35	21.70	56.50	8.70	8.70
Definition of Terms Used	4.35	30.40	47.80	8.70	8.70
Review of Related Literature and Studies	-	17.40	60.90	13.00	8.70

According to the sections of writing an introduction, detail the percentage of the college faculty's responses per section. Table 4 reveals that for the six (6) sections, the faculty's response for *title*, *background*, *framework*, and *review of related literature* ranges from 1, which is interpreted as '*least capable*,' to 4, '*more capable*.' Additionally, the faculty's response to the statement of the problem and definition of terms each range from 1, which is interpreted as '*least capable*,' to 5, '*most capable*.' The result represents an average response. Faculty members' introductions could indicate an average knowledge of the specialized knowledge or expertise in the specific area of research (Tecson-Mendoza, 2015; Caingcoy, 2020; Perez et al., 2022).

Table 5 presents the comparison of the six (6) sections on the research capability of writing an introduction.

Table 5.

Comparison on the research capability on writing an introduction.

Writing An Introduction	Mean	Std. Dev.	Qual. Int.	<i>f</i>	<i>p</i>
Title of the Research Paper	2.96 a	0.928	Capable	0.526	0.756
Background of the Study	2.96 a	0.928	Capable		
Framework of the Study	2.74 a	0.810	Capable		
Statement of the Problem	3.04 a	0.928	Capable		
Definition of Terms Used	3.13 a	0.968	Capable		
Review of Related Literature and Studies	2.87 a	0.815	Capable		
OVERALL	2.95	0.839	Capable		

As presented in Table 5, a one-way ANOVA was performed to compare the different sections of writing an introduction. The result revealed no statistical difference between the writing and the sections of an introduction ($F(5,132)=0.526$, $p=0.756$). Tukey's HSD Test for multiple comparisons found that the mean values of the sections were not significantly different. There was no significant difference in the research capability in writing the sections of an introduction.

Many researchers use a standard structure and methodology when writing an introduction (Christenson et al., 2014). This may result in similar capabilities across individual faculty members when approaching and addressing the mentioned components (Perez et al., 2022; Salom, 2013). Additionally, most researchers receive similar training and education in research methods, including how to write an introduction. These standardized teachings may lead to similar capabilities among the faculty, regardless of the specific components being addressed (Regla & Ballera, 2021; Quitaras & Abuson, 2021). Furthermore, the faculty can access similar resources,

such as scholarly articles, research databases, and academic libraries. These resources can provide valuable information and support when writing the introduction, leading to comparable research capabilities (Vacaldo et al., 2019).

Table 6 summarizes the faculty evaluation on their capability on writing a methodology.

Table 6.

Faculty evaluation on the research capability on writing a methodology.

Writing A Methodology	Percentage				
	5	4	3	2	1
Research Design	-	17.40	56.50	17.40	8.70
Sampling and Sampling Procedure	4.35	17.40	52.20	17.40	8.70
Research Instrument	-	21.70	47.80	21.70	8.70
Data Gathering Procedure	-	26.10	47.80	26.10	8.70

According to the sections of writing a methodology, the study details the percentage of the college faculty's responses per section. Table 6 reveals that for the four (4) sections, the faculty's response for *research design*, *research instrument*, and *data gathering procedure* ranges from 1, interpreted as 'least capable,' to 4, 'more capable.' Additionally, the faculty's responses for the *sample and sampling procedure* have ranged from 1', interpreted as 'least capable,' to 5, 'most capable.' The result represents an average response. The methodology writing skills of faculty members and the percentages presented in Table 6 express an average capacity for specialized knowledge in the specific area of research (Tecson-Mendoza, 2015; Caingcoy, 2020; Perez et al., 2022).

Table 7 presents the comparison of the four (4) sections on the research capability of writing a methodology.

Table 7.

Comparison on the research capability on writing a methodology.

Writing A Methodology	Mean	Std. Dev.	Qual. Int.	<i>f</i>	<i>p</i>
Research Design	2.83 a	0.834	Capable	0.073	0.975
Sampling and Sampling Procedure	2.91 a	0.949	Capable		
Research Instrument	2.83 a	0.887	Capable		
Data Gathering Procedure	2.91 a	0.900	Capable		
OVERALL	2.87	0.849	Capable		

As presented in Table 7, a one-way ANOVA was performed to compare the different sections of writing a methodology. The result revealed no statistical difference between writing the different sections of a methodology ($F(3,88)=0.073$, $p=0.975$). Tukey's HSD Test for multiple comparisons found that the mean values of the sections were not significantly different. There was no significant difference in the research capability in writing the sections of a methodology.

There is a commonly accepted or standardized approach to conducting research in a particular field or discipline (Christenson et al., 2014). The researchers being compared possess similar skills, knowledge, and expertise in research methods and design (Vacaldo et al., 2019; Regla & Ballera, 2021). The faculty have similar training and experience, so, likely, their research capabilities will not significantly differ in terms of writing the methodology section (Perez et al., 2022).

Research Capability of San Isidro College Faculty: Intervention Strategies to Write a Research Paper

Table 8 summarizes the faculty evaluation on their capability on writing the results and discussion.

Table 8.

Faculty evaluation on the research capability on writing the results and discussion.

Writing The Results And Discussion	Percentage				
	5	4	3	2	1
Presentation of Data	-	30.40	39.10	21.70	8.70
Analysis of Data and Findings	4.35	21.70	43.50	21.70	8.70
Making Use of References to Support Findings	4.35	26.10	52.20	8.70	8.70
Summary, Conclusions, and Recommendation	-	26.10	52.20	13.00	8.70

The sections on writing the results and discussion detail the percentage of the college faculty's response per section. Table 8 reveals that for the four (4) sections, the faculty's response for *data presentation* and summary, conclusion, and recommendation each range from 1, which is interpreted as 'least capable' to 4, 'more capable.' Additionally, the faculty's response for *data analysis* and *support* each range from 1, interpreted as 'least capable' to 5, 'most capable.' The college faculty's writing ability on results and discussion of faculty members, as expressed in Table 8, reflects an average capability in specialized knowledge and experience in the specific area of research (Tecson-Mendoza, 2015; Caingcoy, 2020; Perez et al., 2022).

Table 9 presents the comparison of the four (4) sections on the research capability of writing the results and discussion.

Table 9.

Comparison on the research capability on writing the results and discussion.

Writing The Results and Discussion	Mean	Std. Dev.	Qual. Int.	<i>f</i>	<i>p</i>
Presentation of Data	2.91 a	0.949	Capable		
Analysis of Data and Findings	2.91 a	0.996	Capable		
Making Use of References to Support Findings	3.09 a	0.949	Capable	0.175	0.913
Summary, Conclusions, and Recommendation	2.96 a	0.878	Capable		
OVERALL	2.97	0.877	Capable		

As presented in Table 9, a one-way ANOVA was performed to compare the different sections of writing the results and discussion. The result revealed no statistical difference between writing the results and discussion sections ($F(3,88)=0.175$, $p=0.913$). Tukey's HSD Test for multiple comparisons found that the mean values of the sections were not significantly different. There was no significant difference in the research capability in writing the results and discussion sections.

Writing the results and discussion sections requires skills like critical thinking, data interpretation, logical reasoning, and effective communication (Christenson et al., 2014; Caingcoy, 2020). As a result, individuals with strong research capabilities are likely to be proficient in both sections (Perez et al., 2022). Additionally, there are certain conventions and standards that researchers adhere to when writing the results and discussion sections. These guidelines help ensure consistency and accuracy in reporting research findings (Regla & Ballera, 2021). If

researchers follow these standards effectively, it can minimize variations and contribute to similar research capabilities across the sections (Vacaldo et al., 2019).

Table 10 summarizes the faculty evaluation on their capability on citing references.

Table 10.
Faculty evaluation on the research capability on citing the references.

Citing The References	Percentage				
	5	4	3	2	1
References	8.70	17.40	56.50	8.70	8.70

According to the citing sections, the references detail the percentage of the college faculty's responses per section. Table 10 reveals that the faculty's response for *references* ranges from 1, interpreted as 'least capable,' to 5, 'most capable.' The citing proficiency of faculty members and the percentages shown in Table 10 represent an average capability in specific skill and experience in a particular area of research (Tecson-Mendoza, 2015; Caingcoy, 2020; Perez et al., 2022).

Table 11 presents the comparison of the four (4) sections on the research capability of writing a research article.

Table 11.
Comparison on the research capability of the instructors.

Research Capability	Mean	Std. Dev.	Qual. Int.	<i>f</i>	<i>p</i>
Introduction	2.95 a	0.834	Capable	0.233	0.873
Methodology	2.87 a	0.849	Capable		
Results and Discussion	2.97 a	0.877	Capable		
References	3.09 a	0.996	Capable		
OVERALL	2.97	0.881	Capable		

As presented in Table 11, a one-way ANOVA was performed to compare the different sections of writing a research paper. The result revealed no statistical difference between the different sections of a research paper ($F(3,88)=0.233$, $p=0.873$). Tukey's HSD Test for multiple comparisons found that the mean values of the sections were not significantly different. There was no significant difference in the research capability for writing a research paper.

Some college faculty have years of experience in conducting and publishing research. Faculty members must often publish research to advance their academic careers so that they may have honed their research skills over time (Tecson-Mendoza, 2015; Regla & Ballera, 2021). The faculty members often have access to various resources, including academic databases and collaboration opportunities with other experts in their field. This access to resources can enhance their research capabilities and the quality of their papers (Christenson et al., 2014; Caingcoy, 2020).

Research is an iterative process; new studies often build upon existing knowledge. The college faculty members regularly engage with the latest research in their field, keeping them updated with current knowledge. This cumulative knowledge allows faculty members to draw upon existing research and incorporate it into their writings, resulting in consistent quality (Vacaldo et al., 2019). While these factors contribute to the similarity in research capabilities among college faculty, it is

Research Capability of San Isidro College Faculty: Intervention Strategies to Write a Research Paper

essential to note that variations may still exist in terms of research outcomes and expertise within specific sub-fields or disciplines (Quitoras & Abuson, 2021).

Suggested Intervention Strategies

Matrix 1 listed the main themes of the suggested intervention strategies of the college faculty for article submission.

Matrix 1.

Suggested intervention strategies of the college faculty for article submission.

Themes	Respondents	<i>f</i>	%	Rank
Research Advisership and Collaboration	CI-8, CI-19, CI-20	3	13.04	1
Seminar and Workshop	CI-2, CI-11	2	8.70	2
Include as a Faculty Load	CI-15	1	4.35	3
Monetary Incentive	CI-14	1	4.35	3
Recognition	CI-5	1	4.35	3
Publication Support	CI-21	1	4.35	3

A significant portion of the college faculty suggested for research advisership, as highlighted by CI-8 for partnership with experienced faculty members.

“Pair faculty members with experienced researchers or mentors who can guide them.” (CI-8)

Moreover, CI-19 and CI-20 suggested for collaboration and partnerships.

“Create a supportive and collaborative research environment by establishing research groups or communities of practice.” (CI-19)

“Establish collaborations and partnerships between faculty members and external researchers or institutions, which can provide additional motivation and opportunities for publication.” (CI-20)

The suggestion indicates a perceived need for guidance and mentorship in improving research capabilities (Kleyn et al., 2007; Lao et al., 2020). The institution should consider providing resources and support for faculty seeking research guidance (Christenson et al., 2014; Ivanenko et al., 2015; Tecson-Mendoza, 2015).

The college faculty suggested seminars and workshops to enhance their research capabilities as highlighted by CI-2 and CI-11.

“Organize workshops and training sessions on research paper writing.” (CI-2)

“Conduct research capacity building trainings.” (CI-11)

The suggestion indicates that faculty members recognize the importance of continuous learning and professional development in research (Caingcoy, 2020; Quitoras & Abuson, 2021). The institution should offer regular workshops and seminars to support faculty members in improving their research skills (Tecson-Mendoza, 2015; Geiger, 2017; Regla & Ballera, 2021).

The college faculty suggested including research in their faculty load as stated by CI-15.

“Allocate dedicated time for faculty members to engage in research and writing activities, such as adding it to the teaching loads.” (CI-15)

The suggestion indicates that there is a desire among faculty members to allocate more time and resources toward research activities (Salom, 2013; Vacaldo et al., 2019). The institution should consider revising faculty workload policies to ensure adequate time and support for research (Regla & Ballera, 2021; Perez et al., 2022).

A percentage of the college faculty suggested monetary incentives for writing and publishing research papers as suggested by CI-14.

“Provide incentives such as financial rewards or recognition for faculty members who publish research papers in reputable journals.” (CI-14)

The suggestion indicates that faculty members value recognition and rewards for their research efforts (Vacaldo et al., 2019). The institution should consider implementing a system of incentives to motivate and reward research productivity (Ivanenko et al., 2015; Regla & Ballera, 2021).

The college faculty suggested being recognized for their research initiative and publication records as highlighted by CI-5.

“Foster a culture of research and scholarly output by celebrating and recognizing faculty members' research achievements.” (CI-5)

The suggestion indicates a need for acknowledgment and appreciation for research achievements (Caingcoy, 2020; Quitoras & Abuson, 2021). The institution could establish mechanisms to recognize and celebrate faculty members' research contributions, such as awards or honors (Ivanenko et al., 2015; Geiger, 2017; Vacaldo et al., 2019; Perez et al., 2022).

Lastly, the faculty suggested publication support from the institution as highlighted by CI-21.

“Offer publication support services, such as proofreading or formatting assistance, to alleviate faculty members' concerns regarding the technical aspects of manuscript preparation and offer additional research support and resources, such as funding.” (CI-21)

The suggestion indicates that faculty members may require assistance and resources to publish their research (Wa-Mbaleka, 2015; Caingcoy, 2020). The institution should provide support and infrastructure, such as access to publishing platforms or editorial assistance, to facilitate research dissemination (Vacaldo et al., 2019; Quitoras & Abuson, 2021; Perez et al., 2022).

CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATION

The findings of this study regarding college faculty and their experience in publishing research articles reveal a stark contrast. While most faculty members lack any prior experience in this area, suggesting a significant lack of engagement with the publication process, a notable minority have successfully navigated the challenges and requirements associated with publishing their research work. These results highlight the need for increased support and resources to encourage a more significant percentage of college faculty to participate actively in disseminating their scholarly endeavors. By enhancing opportunities for faculty to engage in the publication process, the academic community can benefit from a broader range of insights and findings, contributing to advancing knowledge in various disciplines.

Additionally, the result indicates a general trend of researchers being more inclined to publish their work within their respective institutions and internationally. At the same time, local or

national journal publishing appears less common. The absence of publication in local or national journals can be further investigated to understand the reasons behind this phenomenon, such as limited opportunities or preferences for international exposure. Moreover, the result shows a moderate level of research activity within the institution, with a significant number of the college faculty publishing their research in institutional and international journals. However, only a few prolific researchers have a high publication output.

Furthermore, the results indicate that a higher percentage of the college faculty prefer sole authorship when publishing fewer research articles (1 to 5). However, when it comes to a more significant number of articles (more than 5), a smaller percentage of the faculty tends to have publications in both categories, implying that collaboration is less joint for a higher volume of articles. Less than half of the faculty show moderate research productivity, while a relatively small percentage are highly productive researchers. Additionally, the faculty are more likely to publish papers individually with fewer articles. More than half of the population has some level of research engagement, but only some individuals achieve high research productivity. Nonetheless, the faculty members possess an average level of knowledge, expertise, methodology writing skills, writing ability on results and discussion, and citing proficiency in their specific area of research.

The study recommends (1) providing resources and support for faculty seeking research guidance, such as establishing mentorship programs or providing access to experienced advisers. (2) Offer regular workshops and seminars to support faculty members in improving their research skills and encourage continuous learning and professional development. (3) Revise faculty workload policies to ensure adequate time and support for research activities, addressing the desire among faculty members to allocate more time and resources towards their research. (4) Implement a system of incentives, such as monetary rewards or recognition, to motivate and reward research productivity and acknowledge faculty members' efforts. Additionally, establish mechanisms to recognize faculty members' research contributions, such as awards or honors, to fulfill the need for acknowledgment and appreciation for their research achievements. And (6) provide publication support and resources, such as access to publishing platforms or editorial assistance, to help faculty members in the process of disseminating their research findings.

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